

TYPE 1 DIABETES AS A RISK FACTOR FOR BONE HEALTH IN CHILDHOOD

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Annotation. Diabetes mellitus is a global problem throughout the world. According to WHO, today about 422 million people suffer from diabetes, which is 6.028% of the total population of the planet. [1,2,3]. Diabetes incidence statistics are growing every year. If the situation develops at the same pace, then by 2025 the number of patients with diabetes will double. By 2030, diabetes will become the 7th cause of death worldwide. This problem is also relevant for our country. [4,5]. Over the past 20 years, the number of patients with diabetes in Uzbekistan has tripled. As of January 1, 2019, 336 thousand people were registered, of which (according to the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan): 18 thousand patients with type 1 diabetes, 315 thousand patients with type 2 diabetes; in addition, 434 cases of gestational diabetes and 2648 cases of other specific types of diabetes were recorded. The first type of diabetes occurs due to a lack of insulin. It most often develops in childhood and adolescence, but can also begin in adults. [6,7,8]. The main causes of type 1 diabetes include hereditary predisposition. Diabetes mellitus is not directly inherited, but there are genetic predisposition factors for developing type 1 diabetes. If parents have diabetes, their children are at increased risk of developing the disease. Genetic predisposition plays an important role in the development of type 1 diabetes, but not every person predisposed to it develops the disease. For the occurrence of a disease, triggers are needed - infectious and non-infectious environmental factors. Under the influence of triggers, autoimmune processes are launched and antibodies to the body's own cells begin to be produced, including insulin and the cells of the pancreas, which produces this insulin. Infectious triggers include enteroviruses,

rotaviruses, rubella viruses, chickenpox, mumps, viral hepatitis, cytomegalovirus, Epstein-Barr virus, etc. Among the non-infectious triggers that can lead to type 1 diabetes in a predisposed person are dietary components (gluten, soy, glucose), feeding a young child with cow's milk or a mixed diet based on cow's milk, exposure to heavy metals, nitrites/nitrates, substances toxic to beta cells. [4,5,9]. In addition, psychosocial factors (stress), ultraviolet radiation, temperature/seasonality play a role. As a result of autoimmune processes, the beta cells of the pancreas are destroyed, insulin ceases to be produced, absolute insulin deficiency occurs. Clinically, the disease manifests itself when more than 80% of beta cells are destroyed. The problem of type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) in children is associated with the growing prevalence and severity of complications associated with the impact on general metabolism, including bone tissue. [10,11,12].

Keywords: type 1 diabetes mellitus, viral hepatitis, enteroviruses, rotaviruses, rubella viruses, cytomegalovirus.

Purpose of the study: assessment of bone strength indicators in children with type 1 diabetes according to ultrasound osteodensitometry and markers of bone metabolism.

Materials and research methods: 82 children aged 4 to 15 years were studied, the main group - 41 children with type 1 diabetes mellitus, the control group - 41 children with health group II. An analysis of clinical and anamnestic data was carried out, ultrasound osteodensitometry was carried out using an ultrasonic densitometer "Omnisense omni" (Sunlight Medical Ltd, Israel), equipped with a specialized program and a children's sensor, the level of total calcium (Ca), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), phosphorus (P) was determined on biochemical analyzer Clima MC-15 (Ral, Spain), osteocalcin level and b-CrossLaps (Nordic Bioscience Diagnostics A/S).

Research results. When studying the bone strength of children with T1DM (n=40), it was found that 7.5% (n=3) had a pronounced decrease in bone strength, 15% (n=6) had low strength levels, 55% (n=25) had a tendency to decrease in strength, 22.5%

(n=9) normal strength indicators. A decrease in bone strength in children with T1DM was significantly more common (77.5%; n=31) than in the control group (7.5%; n=3) (p=0.000). Significant differences in bone strength indicators in children with T1DM depending on the presence of antenatal risk factors, physical development, gender, age and pathognomonic clinical manifestations were not identified ($p > \alpha$), differences in Ca content (p = 0.37), P (p = 0.05) was not established between groups of children. In children with T1DM, the level of ALP was significantly lower compared to children in the control group. There was no significant correlation between the parameters of Ca-P metabolism and bone strength ($p \geq 0.05$). A decrease in the level of osteocalcin in children with T1DM occurred significantly more often (100%, n=40) than in children of the control group (2.5%, n=1) (p=0.001), significant differences in the level of osteocalcin were obtained between the children of the main and control groups (Mann-Whitney test p=0.001). Increased levels of b-Crosslaps in children with T1DM were significantly more common (52.5%, n=21) than in children in the control group (22.5%, n=9) (p=0.000). The level of b-Crosslaps is statistically significantly higher in children with type 1 diabetes (Mann-Whitney test p = 0.001). The correlation between bone strength parameters, osteocalcin level (r=-0.26, p=0.036), b-Crosslaps level is significant (r=-0.024, $p > \alpha$). Significant differences in osteocalcin levels were obtained between children of the main and control groups (Mann-Whitney test p = 0.001). Increased levels of b-Crosslaps in children with T1DM were significantly more common (52.5%, n=21) than in children in the control group (22.5%, n=9) (p=0.000). The level of b-Crosslaps is statistically significantly higher in children with type 1 diabetes (Mann-Whitney test p = 0.001). The correlation between bone strength parameters, osteocalcin level (r=-0.26, p=0.036), b-Crosslaps level is significant (r=-0.024, $p > \alpha$). Significant differences in osteocalcin levels were obtained between children of the main and control groups (Mann-Whitney test p = 0.001). Increased levels of b-Crosslaps in children with T1DM were significantly more common (52.5%, n=21)

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Conclusions. Children with T1DM had a high incidence of decreased bone strength. A correlation between bone strength indicators and biochemical markers has been proven, while the determination of standard biochemical indicators of calcium-phosphorus metabolism is uninformative.

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